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CYCLICITY IN UZBEK POETRY OF THE EARLY 20TH CENTURY

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Annotatsiya. This article studies the issue of seriality in Jadid poetry, and also focuses on the problem of the subject that underlies the cycle. In particular, the expression of labor events relevant for that period and the creation of cycle poems about the grief of the Motherland are analyzed. Attention is also paid to Fitrat's scattered cycle poems and lyrical cycles related to the description of nature in the work of Cholpon.

Keywords: labourer stories, imagery, lyrical hero, letter form, poetic observation, description of experience, prose poem, landscape lyrics, etc.

INTRODUCTION

The fact that Jadid poetry was a leader in covering the problems of social life is understood from the expression of current issues in this poetry. In particular, the interpretation of current issues such as the life of the people, their problems, the freedom of the nation, education are among them. Among such issues, the issues related to forced labor are also reflected as an unacceptable process that brought misfortune to the nation, which reveals the attitude of the Jadids to this issue.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Genres and forms chosen for poetic cycles, their specific characteristics, are studied mainly on the example of the works of artists of the 20th century, because the best examples of lyric cycles were created in the literature of this period. Examples of Eastern folklore and literature, in particular, in the works of Jalaluddin Rumi, Fariddin Attar, Jami, Alisher Navoi, Bedil, there are extremely conditional figurative and symbolic images, the large-scale content of which does not fit into the subject image. In Uzbek literature, there are various examples of metaphor in the works of Hamza, Gafur Ghulam, Hamid Olimjon, Ghairatiy, and later Erkin Vahidov, Abdulla Oripov. This is especially evident in the analysis of lyrical cycles created by artists such as Rauf Parfi, Eshqabil Shukur, Bahrom Rozimuhammad, Tursun Ali. The article effectively used comparative-typological, artistic analysis, genetic, and structural methods.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The ideas that the development of series in Uzbek literary studies began with folk oral works are presented in the research of professor and major folklore scholar Tora Mirzayev (Mirzayev T. *Silsila dostonlar.* – T., Sharq. 2006), the ideas that Uzbek folk epics have aspects such as gradualism and consistency according to their specific characteristics are presented in the research of another folklore scholar Salimakhon Mirzayeva (Mirzayeva S. *Poetics of Uzbek folk romance epics.* – T., Fan. 2004), the ideas that the experience of cycle works can be observed in poetic epics, which are examples of the lyric-epic genre, are presented in the research of literary scholar, professor Nomon Rahimjonov (Rahimjonov N. *Evolutions in artistic thought.* – T., Tamaddun, 2008), and the

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-12

information about the existence of poetic cycles in the work of one of the classical creators, Usmonkhodja Zoriy. Dildorahon Abdullayeva (Abdullaeva D.Z. Usmonkhodja Zoriy hayoti. – T., Yangi asr avlody, 2005). Literary critic Hamid Mirzayev (Mirzayev H. A series of sonnets in Uzbek poetry // Uzbek language and literature. 2007. Issue 1) discussed the sonnet cycle in Uzbek literature, while S. Rahmonova (Rahmonova S. Uzbek sonnets: poetic structure and artistic image. Candidate of Philological Sciences ... diss... author's ref. – T.: 2010) studied the issue of poetic structure and artistic concept in the sonnet cycle. Aldasheva Shirin (Aldasheva Sh.J. The nature of quatrains, octaves and poetic series in Uzbek lyrics of the 70s-80s. Candidate of Philological Sciences ... diss... author's ref. - T.: 2019) partially studied the nature of poetic series in Uzbek lyrics of the 70s-80s. As can be seen from the above, it can be said that the relevance of studying the poetic series and its compositional structure was a necessity for a deep and comprehensive study of the literature of the second half of the 20th century, and the development of a theoretical concept from them.

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In particular, four poems by Abdulla Avloni under the title “Mardikorlar ashuvlasi” are dedicated to this very topic, and the poems are written in the forms of masnavi and ghazal. This series includes poems such as “A worker’s father’s words to his son”, “A mother’s words to her son”, “A son’s words to his mother”, “A wife’s words”, which reflect the events of the 1916 labor movement. These poems highlight the farewell moments and injustices of the children of the country who were taken far from their homeland, to the snowy and icy lands of the north, to serve in the front line. Although the tone and style of the poems resemble folk songs, the poems "The Words of a Laborer's Father to His Son" and "The Words of His Mother to His Son" are written in the form of a masnavi, while poems such as "The Words of His Son to His Mother" and "The Words of His Wife" are written in the ghazal genre. In particular, the poem "The Words of a Laborer's Father to His Son" describes what a father says while observing his son:

With how much effort, my son, I used to raise you,
I was so sad for you that my soul was consumed.
If you leave, I will remain, my eyes will be filled with tears,
This separation will burn and become a fire. [Abdulla Avloniy. 2022. 162]

That is, the lyrical hero in the poem is the father, and the suffering of the heart is expressed through his language. In the poem “The words of a mother to her son”: My dear son, my dear son, may God be your light,

May God be your caretaker day and night on the road and in the desert. [Abdulla Avloniy. 2022. 162] This poem describes a mother praying for her son to be saved from misfortunes. In the poem “His words to his mother”, the child’s farewell words to his mother, along with his love for her, are expressed:

O my dear mother, who caused my existence,
You were the soul of my body – my life, my eternal life [Abdulla Avloniy. 2022. 163].
The poem "Words to His Wife" reflects the farewell words of a young man leaving for work:
Stay well, O caring one, whether I see you or not,
O the light of my eyes is bright, whether I see you or not [Abdulla Avloniy. 2022. 164].

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

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It seems that the theme of labor has acquired special importance in Avloni's poetry. In addition, Avloni's poems such as "A lament over the state of the nation", "I am helpless in my own country", "A voice from the soil of Turkestan", "An appeal to the soil of Turkestan", "School" (two poems), "Education is rare", "From our own life", "A view from our own life" also formed small groups with educational content. All of them have almost the same content, which is to show the backwardness of Turkestan and to call on the children of their own nation to contribute to the prosperity of the Motherland through education.

In the poetry of Hamza Hakimzoda Niyozzi, the group of "Poems of Labor" ("Longing", "Salam ayting") is created in the form of quatrains and duotones in the finger system. Hamza's poem "Sog'inib" rhymes in the form of a murabba'. The rhyme scheme is also in the form a-a-a-b, c-c-c-b.

Don't touch me too hard, my chief,
My tears are flowing from my mouth,
My heart is crushed beyond measure,
My homeland, my people, I miss you [Hamza Hakimzoda Niyozzi.1958. 50].

The poem "Salom ayting" is sung on behalf of a young man who is escorting a person from his neighborhood home, and it reflects the young man's strong longing for his homeland and family:

Brother, if you are healthy, first
Say hello to your fathers.
The brave man who ran out

Say hello to your mothers [Hamza Hakimzoda Niyozzi. 1958. 51].

The form of this poem by Hamza is reminiscent of the rhyme scheme and external structure of the stanzas. The first five verses in this stanza rhyme the same, while the last stanza of the remaining stanzas continues to rhyme like the first stanza. That is, in the form of a-b-a-b-a-b-a-b, c-c-c-c-c-c-c-c-a-b. This stanza structure gave rise to a new form called stanza.

Abdurauf Fitrat formed his series "The Sorrow of the Homeland" in the form of a sophistic poem, consisting of such parts as "The Sorrow of the Homeland", "From an Uzbek Language", and "Temur is Ahead". The poems reflect the remembrance of the glorious past of the Motherland and concern for its future, typical of the Jadids:

O Great Turan, land of lions!
What happened to you? How are you?
How many days have you been gone?
O glorious cradle of Genghis, Timur, Oghuz, Attila!
Where are those high places from which you have ascended?
Why did you descend into the pits of slavery?

Where are your tiger-hearted children who make the world tremble with their "urho"?
[Abdurauf Fitrat. 2022. 32]

This collection of poems in Fitrat's work is one of the examples that experimentally proves that it is possible to create a collection even in a free form.

The small series called "From the Book of Nature" in Cholpon's work consists of sections such as "First Page" and "Second Page". "First Page" reflects the poet's images of nature flourishing, of trees on the surface of the earth being children of Mother Earth, and of them being able to live happily if nothing disturbs their bliss:

My dear... the peaceful sleep of the earth is disturbed,
A strong sigh has stretched from To...'s heart.

... The wish of every leaf to nature:

Not to break the root of this life,

Not to disturb this pleasure, this pleasure. [Abdulhamid Cholpon. 2022. 123]. The content of the poem "Second Page" is the opposite of the situation in the above poem, in which the trees, which are children of the Earth, are attacked, they are chopped down with an axe, and are exposed:

Another season... the earth lies panting,

Every time it passes, it shoots its poison.

...The axes that have split the wood

Also crush the soft bosom of the earth.

How many times in one miserable day

It adorns with its being, its life [Abdulhamid Chulpon. 2022. 124].

The image of nature, mother Earth and trees, which is the refuge of man, is formed on two different backgrounds: happiness and tragedy, which enhances the impact of the poem.

Two poems in the sub-series of Cholpon's "Daughter of the Nile" are also created in the same way by contrasting them using two different images. The first poem, "First Song", depicts Falloh's happiness in her youth and her final misfortune after losing her lover, and then "Second Song" depicts her as an unfortunate person who has lost her freedom and has not found happiness in her work. One of the poems is formed using a four-line stanza in the finger system, and the other is formed using a two-line stanza in the same system.

Thus, in Jadid poetry, it can be seen that poetic series are reflected on the theme of labor events, on the theme of national grief - nationalism, and as examples of landscape lyrics related to the image of nature. These series are created using various poetic forms in different genres, based on the artistic concept and creative intention of the poets. In genre poems, the issue of imagery is also formulated in a unique way, appropriate to the subject.

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THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

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